

ISic0636

I.Sicily inscription 0636

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2011.04.20

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Euryelos (?)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 104860

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332963

1. [Αὐτοκράτωρ Καῖσαρ θεοῦ Ἰουλίου υἱὸς]
2. [ἕπατος τὸ τ] ρί[τον καθεσταμένος τὸ τέτα]ρτον (vac.unknown)
3. [---κατε]σκεύα [σεν---τὰν γέφ]υρα ὕ [συνάπτουσιν πρὸς τὰ]ν Ἀχραδίν α [ν]
4. [καὶ --- ἀνέστασεν ---] τὰς Νί [κας --- ἐν τᾷ] ἐξ [έδραι --- καὶ --- τὰ ἀγάλμ]ατα α
[---]

Edition: PHI331827

1. [Αὐτοκράτωρ Καῖσαρ θεοῦ Ἰουλίου υἱὸς . . . ἕπατος τὸ τ]ρί[τον, καθεσταμ(ένος) τὸ τέτα]ρτον, [ἐκ θεμελίων κατε]σκεύα[σεν τὰν γέφ]υρα[ν συνάπτουσιν πρὸς τὰ]ν Ἀχραδίνα[ν καὶ ἀνέστασεν — —] τὰς Νί[κας ἐν τᾷ] ἐξ[έδραι — — καὶ τὰ ἀγάλμ]ατα [— —].

2.

Apparatus

Text via PHI: highly conjectural restorations by Manganaro

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

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Fragment a, photo J. Prag